

A Novel Approach to Phenylcoumarins*

A. K. Das Gupta and M. S. Paul

Coumarins having a phenyl substitution in the α -pyrone ring have previously been synthesised¹ by Perkin-type reaction or by other methods. These substances have estrogenic² and other interesting optical brightening properties³. The authors wish to report a direct synthesis of 3- and 4-phenyl derivatives of 7-hydroxydihydrocoumarin and the corresponding 3,4-diphenyl derivative by the zinc chloride-catalyzed reaction of resorcinol with the appropriate phenyl substituted acrylonitriles. These dihydrocoumarins on dehydrogenation over palladium-charcoal (10%) gave the corresponding coumarins.

General Procedure : Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through a well stirred ice cold solution of resorcinol (0.1 m), phenyl acrylonitrile (0.1 m) in dry ether (50 ml) with portionwise addition of fused $ZnCl_2$ (0.1 m). The mixture was stirred in cold for 2–3 hrs and left in the refrigerator for 3–5 days. Ether was decanted off and the thick liquid decomposed with cold dilute hydrochloric acid followed by heating on a steam bath. After cooling and usual work up the mixture afforded the dihydrocoumarins which were purified by evaporative distillation and crystallisation. The dihydrocoumarins on boiling in diphenyl ether with Pd-C (10%) for 5–6 hrs afforded the coumarins in a good overall yield (60–65%).

* Part XII of a series—Coumarin and Related Compounds.

1. (a) N. P. Buu Hoi, B. Eckert and R. Roger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1948;
 (b) L. L. Woods and J. Sapp, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 3703;
 (c) G. N. Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 645;
 (d) H. Merrwin, E. Büchner and K. van Emster, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, **152**(2), 237;
 (e) T. R. Seshadri and S. Varadarajan, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **35A**, 75;
 (f) K. Sato and T. Amakasu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 2446.
2. (a) N. P. Buu Hoi and B. Eckert, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1931;
 (b) D. Lednicer, S. C. Lyster and G. W. Duncan, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 725.
3. R. Raue, Ger. pat., 1, 102,694 (*C.A.*, 1961, **55**, 24034^d).

3-Phenyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (II) : From α -phenyl acrylonitrile, colourless needles, m.p. 154–155° (toluene). ν_{max} 1760 (lactone); acetate m.p. 149–150°. Dehydrogenation over Pd-C afforded 3-phenyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (V) m.p. 204–205° (ethyl acetate) (*lit.*⁴, 206–207°).

*4-Phenyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin*⁵ (III) : Colourless prisms m.p. 140–141° (toluene), ν_{max} 1730 (lactone), acetate m.p. 87–88°. Dehydrogenation gave 4-phenyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (VI) m.p. and mixed m.p. 245–246° (*lit.*⁶, 245°).

3,4-Diphenyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (IV) : From $\alpha\beta$ -diphenyl acrylonitrile, colourless needles, m.p. 211–212° (toluene), ν_{max} 1740 (lactone). On dehydrogenation it afforded 3,4-diphenyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (VII) m.p. and mixed m.p. 283–284° (*lit.*^{1a}, 285–286°).

Similar studies are being extended to other systems.

We thank Mr. P. Bagchi, Director of Research for encouragement.

Research Division,
East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd.,
Calcutta-60.

Received May 26, 1970

4. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2898.
5. The reaction was performed with β -phenyl methyl acrylate and anhydrous aluminium chloride at 0° for 3 hrs at 140–160°.
6. A. Sonn, *Chem. Ber.*, 1918, 51, 1829